

REVIEW OF ‘NASA HI SHIRASO DVARAM’ WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO NASYA KARMA IN PRESENT CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

The verse “Nasa hi śirasō dvāram” is a famous Ayurvedic statement that means, “The nose is indeed the gateway to the head.” This principle forms the basis of Nasya Karma, one of the five major Panchakarma therapies. According to Ayurveda, the nose provides direct access to the Sira (head region), which includes the brain, sensory organs, and vital channels located above the clavicle. Therefore, medicines administered through the nasal route can reach and influence these structures more effectively than some other routes of administration. It is really a wonderful way to assess the brain where oral medicaments have restricted entry due to Blood Brain Barrier. When medicated oils, herbal juices, powders, or ghee are instilled into the nostrils during Nasya, they are believed to eliminate accumulated Doshas (especially Kapha) from the head and neck region and nourish and strengthen the organs of the head. Further it improves the functioning of the nose, eyes, ears, throat, and brain and promote mental clarity, memory, and sensory perception. Since the nose is the gateway to the head, medicines administered through it spread throughout the cranial region and help eliminate the morbid Doshas located there. Significance in Nasya is its use for conditions such as Headache, Sinusitis, Allergic rhinitis, Cervical stiffness, Facial paralysis and Certain eye, ear, and throat disorders. Thus, “Nasa hi śirasō dvāram” emphasizes the therapeutic importance of the nasal route in Ayurveda and serves as the fundamental rationale for Nasya therapy.

Key words – Nasa, Nasya, Panchakarma, olfactory nerves, Ayurveda

1. INTRODUCTION

Acceptance and rejection of all senses is carried out through the indriyas, so it is important to keep knowledge about the microanatomy and physiology of the sense organs. Ayurveda describes the sense organs according to their functional and mythological view; but now it is possible to explore them on the basis of modern functional anatomy. “Nasa hi shiraso dvaram” is a famous verse written by Acharya Vagbhatt in Ashtanga hridayam, for the treatment of diseases of head by nasal insufflations of drugs. It was believed that the drugs given through this route acts directly over brain and heals the lesion, away from it, it was also used in the treatment of the diseases of the Urdhva jatru i.e. of neck, nose, scalp, hair and facial disorders. So, in the present study we have explored a possible correlation between the nose and brain.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURES

A. Embryological correlatio

On the basis of embryological development, it is evident that cerebral hemispheres and olfactory tract have same route of development; and both of them are derivative of the Prosencephalon. We have seen that the prosencephalon is subdivisible in to a median diencephalon and two lateral telencephalic vesicles. The telencephalic vesicles give origin, on either side, to the cerebral cortex and the corpus striatum. The diencephalon gives rise to the thalamus, hypothalamus and related structures. The cavity of the diencephalon forms the third ventricle, while the cavities of the two telencephalic vesicles form the lateral ventricles. From the developmental point of view the cerebral cortex consists of the hippocampal cortex, the pyriform cortex and the neocortex. The developing telencephalon has a medial wall a superolateral wall and a basal striatal region. The hippocampal cortex develops in to the medial wall, the pyriform cortex in the marginal layer superficial to the corpus striatum, and the neocortex in the superolateral region. During development the superior part of the hippocampal cortex becomes separated and remains rudimentary as indusium griseum. While the lower part under goes greater development and becomes the hippocampus and the dentate gyrus. The pyriform cortex also remains relatively small; it gives rise to the part of the cerebral cortex that receives olfactory sensations. It forms the uncus, the anterior part of the Para hippocampal gyrus and the anterior

perforated substance. In contrast to the hippocampal and pyriform cortex the neo cortex under goes very great expansion. It forms the whole of the cerebral cortex seen on the superolateral and medial surfaces of the hemisphere, and the cortex of the inferior surface excluding the pyriform area. So, it can be said that tract of olfaction is directly related to the cerebral cortex, because both of them have the same route of development and are interconnected after development.

B. Anatomical correlation-

On observation based on anatomical point of view the structure of olfactory sensation are described with in the parts of limbic system, and Limbic system is the main centre for psychic abnormality, further we evaluate the structures cover under limbic system and olfactory sensation.

The Limbic system-

The ring like cortex of the cerebral hemisphere surrounding the corpus callosum and dinecephalon constitutes the 'Limbic system'. Broca in 1878 coined this term to refer to this cortex, limbus means a margin. Its continuity with the olfactory bulb through the olfactory striae at the anterior perforated substance is responsible for its association with olfaction and its older name of 'rhinencephalon' or 'smell brain'. However, humans have a limited olfactory sense, so apart from olfaction it is now known to play a role in functions like behavioral activity, primitive emotions, memory and regulation of viscera and so it is also referred to as 'visceral brain'.

From evolutionary point of view in the lowest vertebrates the function of cerebral cortex appears to be almost olfactory. In the further evolutionary development of higher mammals, the olfactory areas of the cortex have become completely overshadowed by non olfactory areas, and in humans the former are reduced to almost insignificant proportions but they are capable of influencing different aspects of cortical activity and so rhiencephalon forms a fundamental portion of the limbic system.

Olfactory pathways-

The olfactory pathways comprised of Olfactory nerves, bulbs, tract, trigone, striae etc; situated at the upper most part of the nose.

Olfactory nerves-

These about twenty in number arise from olfactory mucus membrane situated in the upper part of the nasal cavity above the level of the superior conchae. Bundle of these olfactory nerve fibers pass through the openings of the cribriform plate of the ethmoid bone to enter the olfactory bulb in the cranial cavity.

Olfactory bulb-

The olfactory bulb is an oval flattened strip of grey matter lying on the cribriform plate of ethmoid pressed against the orbital surface of the frontal lobe of the brain. It receives the olfactory nerves from the olfactory zone of the nasal cavity.

Olfactory tract-

Olfactory tract lies in the olfactory sulcus on the orbital surface of the frontal lobe and proceeds backwards from each olfactory bulb to the region of the anterior perforated substance on the base of the brain, where it divides in to lateral, intermediate and medial olfactory striae.

Anterior olfactory nucleus-

It is made up of scattered neurons within the olfactory tract. It sends axons through the anterior commissure to excite the inhibitory neurons on the contralateral bulb.

Olfactory trigone-

It is flattened part of the olfactory tract, near the anterior perforated substance, before it divides in to striae.

Olfactory striae-

Three striae are derived from each olfactory tract; lateral olfactory striae is by far the most important of the three. It skirts the anterior margin of the anterior perforated substance, passes at first laterally on the antero-inferior part of the insula and then makes a sharp kink to turn medially and backwards in the deep depression between the orbital surface of the frontal lobe and the temporal lobe to reach the uncus where it terminates. Olfactory receptive area is located in the uncus and adjacent portion of the hippocampal gyrus. Intermediate olfactory stria terminates in the olfactory tubercle, an area of cortex rostral to the anterior perforated substance. Medial olfactory striae curve medially to reach the medial surface of the cerebral hemisphere, where it blends with the cortex immediately in front of the lamina terminalis. There is no good evidence to indicate that

it constitutes a direct pathway for impulses from the olfactory bulb. Impulses from the olfactory bulb are conveyed to olfactory areas for subjective appreciation of odors and aromas.

The limbic system is considered to be the anatomic substrate underlying behavioral and emotional expression. It expresses itself through the hypothalamus via the autonomic nervous system. Its chief functions are perception of sense of smell (Rhinencephalon), food and sex behavior, Visceral functions responsible for emotions, memory and behavior.

C. Physiological correlation-

Taste and smell, to some extents are mutually complementary; hence term flavor is used for the combined effect of taste and smell. In some animals the ability to smell is extraordinarily developed, such animals are called as “macrosomatic” e.g. dog and by contrast the man and many other mammals are “microsomatic” animals. The area, which constitutes the fundamental area for smelling is called as the olfactory area.

Microscopic features-

The general lining epithelium of the olfactory area is pseudo stratified columnar epithelium. Lying within these cells, there are receptor cells of olfaction, which are the peripheral most part of the neuron (primary olfactory neuron) that carries the impulse of olfaction towards the brain. The receptor cells are surrounded by supporting cells. The most peripheral part of the receptor cell is called as olfactory rod. From each olfactory rod portion, 15-20 cilia project in to the cavity of the nostril. Within these cilia, lie particles called intra membranous particles. These intra membranous particles belong to the group of particles, called ‘molecular receptive apparatus’. Molecules emanating from an odorant are dissolved in the mucus of the olfactory area and then come in contact with the intra membranous particles to produce the sense of odor. There are about 10-20 million of receptor cells in both the nostrils of a man. The rod of the receptor cell is considered to be the dendron of this neuron, from each receptor cell emerges axon fibers which together constitute the olfactory nerve. The receptor cells of the olfactory area have a short span of life, after a few weeks they die and are cast off and are replaced by new receptor cells. This is a very unusual thing for a neuron to shed off and get replaced.

Anatomically these receptor cells are the only neurons of our body which project to the external world.

Mechanism of olfaction-

Volatile molecules from an odorant substance are carried by air, reach the olfactory area, get dissolved in the mucus, in solution form it comes in contact with the intra membranous particle contained within the cilia of the receptor cells and combine with these particles. Then it will generate a receptor potential, which produces impulses in the axons emerging from the receptor cells and reaches to brain.

Further the olfactory tubercle receives inputs from 2 major sources 1. from the olfactory bulb, 2. from the substantia nigra of mid brain via dopaminergic fibers. As substantia nigra is a part of basal ganglia and have dopaminergic fibers, so it is strongly connected with Schizophrenia. Thus, olfactory tubercle may be related to abnormal olfactory perceptions in schizophrenia. Efferent fibers from the tubercle goes to limbic system, thus smell is associated with emotion and behavior. Efferent fibers from the tubercle go to the hypothalamus, thus olfaction is associated with appetite and social behavior.

To reach the primary olfactory cortex, only two neurons are required, which is rather exceptional in sensory physiology. Further, from the primary olfactory cortex, nerve impulses go to terminate on secondary olfactory cortex and other parts of Limbic system nuclei. Thus, smell sensation influences various behaviors and arouses sex behavior. To reach the cortex, the neurons do not have to relay at thalamus, which is exceptional. In fact, this is the only sense which does not relay at thalamus or metathalamus.

D. Clinical correlation-

An intact limbic system with the hypothalamus and brain stem appears to be necessary for fully integrated and prolonged homeostasis under a wide variety of environmental conditions. It is a centre for emotional integration, so the disorders largely caused by its malfunction are mainly psychogenic in origin and which are follows-

1. Disorders of mood and thought are believed to originate in the limbic system resulting in Schizophrenia which is characterized by blunting of emotional responses and thought disorders, depression and anxiety, amnesia and phobias.

2. A lesion that affects the uncus and amygdaloid body may cause “uncinate fits” characterized by unpleasant odor.
3. Lesions involving the hippocampus may lead to an impairment of memory of recent events and also to emotional disturbances. Memory loss should be associated with hippocampal pathology.

Nasya (Nasal instillation)-

Nasya is an Ayurvedic Panchakarma procedure wherein medicaments are instilled into the nasal cavity in doshas especially pertaining to uttamanga, to achieve desired multidimensional effects, it is also known as Siro virechana. It is of five types depending on the medicaments used like it is Navana (medicated oil), Avapida (fresh juices of plants), Pradhamana (medicated powders), Dhumapana (medicated fumes and smokes) and Marsha & Pratimarsha (very small quantity of oil). Further on the basis of their action these are of three types Rechana (purificatory), Brinhana (nourishing) and Shamana (palliative).

Indications of Nasya karma-

It is advised to use this procedure as a purificatory procedure before all promotive and preventive measures, further it should be done before administration of rejuvenating (Rasayana) and virilizing (Bajikarana) therapy. It is also indicated for the treatment of Urdhvajatrugata rogas (Head, Neck and Throat disorders). The other indications are Danta gata roga (dental diseases), Peenasa (chronic rhinitis), Timira (Cataract), Ardhabhedaka (Migraine), Ardita (Facial palsy), Apatantraka (Hysteria), Apatanaka (Convulsions), Galaganda (Thyroid disorders), Swarabheda (Dysarthria), Shirashula (Headache), Unmada (Schizophrenia), Apasmara (Epilepsy), Manyastambha (Cervical spondylitis) and Muka, Minmina, gadagad (dumbness, slurring of speech) etc.

Contra indication of Nasya karma-

Nasya should not to be done in following disorders like Bhukta (Just after meal), Ajirna (Indigestion), After sirah snana (just after head bath), Sneha peeta (after oily diet), Kshudita (Very hungry), Pipasita (Thirsty), Shoka (In grief), Garbhini (Pregnancy), Balak (infants), Nutana Pratishyay (acute Rhinitis), After virechana and anuvasana vasti, Nava jvara (acute fever) and Murchcha (in Unconscious patient) etc.

Time of administration-

According to dosha predominance for Kapha disorders morning time is preferred, for Pitta afternoon is suitable time while for Vata disorders nasya should be given at evening time. It is advised for all persons between the age group of 7 to 80 years

Dose determination of Nasya

When index finger is dipped upto two parwas (joints) in drava dravya (liquid drug) and taken out the amount of Drava (liquid) falling from it is considered as one bindu. Approximately one bindu is 0.5 ml (for oil) Sneha nasya 10/8/6 bindu respectively for uttama, madhyama and avara matra

Before Procedure (Poorva karma)-

Patient is advised to wash face and mouth with Luke warm water. Abyanga is done over shiras, lalata, kapala, greeva & skanda. Nadisveda or tapasveda can be done. Abhyanga over palm and sole can be done. Dhoomapana can be done for srotoshodhana (in case of nasal congestion). Eyes are bandaged with a clean gauze piece after placing lotus petals and cotton pad over closed eyelids. Then Nadi sveda is done (urdhwajatru). Dhoomapana can be done for srotoshodhana, if necessary. Patient is made to lie in supine position with slightly elevated legs and head extended backwards.

Main Procedure (Pradhana karma)-

The medicine mildly warmed over a water bath. The prescribed dose of medicine is taken in the gokarna and poured into either nostril closing the other in a continuous single stream. Immediately after instillation of medicine mild massage should be done over pani, pada, greeva and skanda. Mridu svedana can be done in the above-mentioned areas with suitable method (Hasthasveda or vaspasveda). Patient is asked to inhale the medicine with moderate force and to spit it through mouth turning head to either side alternatively without rising from the cot. Patient is made to lie in the same position for 100 matra kala (3-5 minutes)

After Procedure (Paschat karma)-

Dhoomapana is done with appropriate drugs according to the type of Nasya. Kavala with warm water is done to attain kantha shudhi. The talam should be wiped off

and dry powder (used for preparing talam) is gently rubbed over the anterior frontanale. It is advisable not to take any type of food 2 hrs prior to and 1 hour after nasya. Na-atidrava annapana is indicated in nasya.

Precautions-

While positioning the patient for nasya, if the head is not sufficiently bent the nasya dravya will not enter shiras and if the head is more bent dravya may enter mastulunga and cause complications like headache, dizziness etc. If the spitting is not done properly, or medicine is swallowed, it will cause kaphotklesha, agnimandya and the disease aggravates. If patient spits on one side only, then proper spreading of medicine would not take place. If the patient talk, sneezes, laughs or gets angry or excessively moves his head while doing nasya, the nasya dravya would not reach expected site and instead causes complications like cough, sinusitis rhinorrhoea, and head ache. Patient must avoid exposure to dust, sun breeze, drinking excessive water, alcohol, sneha dravya, bathing, excessive walking etc. Head bathing should be avoided during nasya period (since nasya arhas are almost snana anarhas), if bath is not contraindicated it can be given after 3 hours.

3. CONCLUSION

Psychic disorders are going to be challenging day by day, so an effective measure must be searched to evaluate their exact pathology and treatment methodology. The oldest medical literature available in the world is Ayurveda and one of its famous quotes is “Nasa hi shiraso dvaram” or Nose is the pathway to enter the brain. Psychic abnormalities must be having some connection with the sense of smell as it is a belief that to control mental disorders, strong fetid or pleasant odor must be smelled by the diseased. After evaluating the above embryological, anatomical, physiological and clinical correlation it is clear to say that Nose have a strong connection with the brain and able to play a key role in the generation of psychic disorders so the drugs given through the nasal insufflations may heal the pathology effectively. Away from it modern anti psychotic medicines too can act better if they have used in nasal drop form, it will be also useful to minimize their side effects.

Nasya is a specialized therapeutic procedure in Ayurveda that involves the administration of herbal oils, powders, juices, or medicated preparations through the

nasal route. It is considered one of the Panchakarma therapies and is primarily used for the prevention and treatment of disorders affecting the head, neck, and sensory organs. According to Ayurvedic principles, the nose serves as the gateway to the head, allowing medicines to reach and influence vital structures. Nasya is indicated in conditions such as sinusitis, headaches, allergic rhinitis, cervical stiffness, neurological disorders, and certain eye, ear, and throat diseases. The procedure typically includes preparatory measures, administration of the medicine, and post-procedure care to enhance therapeutic efficacy. Modern research suggests that intranasal delivery may facilitate rapid absorption and direct access to the central nervous system. Nasya is valued for its potential to improve respiratory health, mental clarity, and overall well-being, making it an important component of Ayurvedic preventive and curative healthcare.

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